

Selected Exercises and Proofs in Discrete and Asymptotic Mathematics

Nathaniel Nadler

November 2025

Introduction

This short collection presents a series of self-contained proofs exploring foundational ideas in asymptotic analysis, combinatorics, and graph theory. The problems are adapted from *Polynomial Methods and Incidence Theory* by Dr. Adam Sheffer. My goal was to write each proof in a way that's concise, readable, and conceptually clear—emphasizing structure and reasoning over computation.

1 Exercise A.1

Prove that the bound $f(n)^2 = O(g(n)^2 + h(n)^2)$ implies the bound $f(n) = O(g(n) + h(n))$.

Proof.

Assume

$$f(n)^2 \leq C_1(g(n)^2 + h(n)^2).$$

Taking square roots of both sides, we have

$$f(n) \leq \sqrt{C_1} \sqrt{g(n)^2 + h(n)^2}.$$

Let $C_2 = \sqrt{C_1}$. Then

$$f(n) \leq C_2 \sqrt{g(n)^2 + h(n)^2}.$$

By the inequality

$$\sqrt{a^2 + b^2} \leq |a| + |b|,$$

which follows from $a^2 + b^2 \leq (|a| + |b|)^2$, we get

$$f(n) \leq C_2(|g(n)| + |h(n)|).$$

Thus,

$$f(n) \leq C_2(g(n) + h(n)),$$

and therefore,

$$f(n) = O(g(n) + h(n)).$$

Q.E.D.

2 Exercise A.2

(a). Prove that $k^n = O(n!)$ holds for every $k \in \mathbb{R}$.

Proof.

We aim to show that there exist constants $C > 0$ and $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$|k|^n \leq C n! \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_0.$$

Case 1: $|k| \leq 1$

$$|k|^n \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } n.$$

Thus, for any constant $C \geq 1$,

$$|k|^n \leq C n!.$$

Hence, $k^n = O(n!)$ when $|k| \leq 1$.

Case 2: $|k| > 1$

Consider the ratio

$$\frac{|k|^n}{n!} = \frac{|k|}{1} \cdot \frac{|k|}{2} \cdot \frac{|k|}{3} \cdots \frac{|k|}{n}.$$

Since n grows without bound, eventually $n > |k|$, and for all $j > |k|$,

$$\frac{|k|}{j} < 1.$$

Thus, each factor in the product becomes less than 1, causing the product

$$\frac{|k|^n}{n!}$$

to decrease monotonically toward 0. Therefore,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|k|^n}{n!} = 0.$$

This implies that there exists some n_0 such that for all $n \geq n_0$,

$$\frac{|k|^n}{n!} < 1,$$

or,

$$|k|^n \leq n!.$$

Accordingly, for every real k , there exists a constant $C > 0$ such that

$$|k|^n \leq C n!.$$

$$\boxed{k^n = O(n!)} \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{R}. \quad \text{Q.E.D.}$$

(b). Prove that $n! = O(n^n)$.

Proof.

Consider the ratio

$$\frac{n!}{n^n} = \frac{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdots n}{n \cdot n \cdot n \cdots n} = \frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{2}{n} \cdot \frac{3}{n} \cdots \frac{n}{n}.$$

Since n is arbitrarily large, there are $n - 1$ terms of the product satisfying $\frac{i}{n} < 1$ and one term (the last one) equal to 1. Hence,

$$\frac{n!}{n^n}$$

is a product of terms less than or equal to 1, with at least one strictly less than 1 for all $n > 1$. Consequently, this product decreases monotonically toward 0 as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n!}{n^n} = 0.$$

This implies that there exists n_0 such that for all $n \geq n_0$,

$$\frac{n!}{n^n} < 1,$$

or equivalently,

$$n! \leq C n^n$$

for some constant $C > 0$.

Therefore,

$$\boxed{n! = O(n^n)}. \quad \text{Q.E.D.}$$

3 Exercise A.3

Find a function $f(n)$ such that $f(n) = \Omega(n^k)$ for all $k > 0$, and $f(n) = O(k^n)$ for all $k > 1$.

Solution.

We want something that grows faster than any polynomial, but slower than any exponential.

A good guess for this kind of growth is:

$$f(n) = 2^{(\log n)^2}.$$

Let's check that it actually works.

1. Showing $f(n) = \Omega(n^k)$ for all $k > 0$.

We can rewrite n^k in base 2:

$$n^k = 2^{k \log n}.$$

So the ratio is

$$\frac{f(n)}{n^k} = \frac{2^{(\log n)^2}}{2^{k \log n}} = 2^{(\log n)^2 - k \log n}.$$

For any fixed k , $(\log n)^2$ eventually gets way bigger than $k \log n$ as n grows, so the exponent goes to infinity. That means

$$\frac{f(n)}{n^k} \rightarrow \infty,$$

and therefore $f(n)$ grows faster than any polynomial.

2. Showing $f(n) = O(k^n)$ for all $k > 1$.

Again, write k^n as $2^{n \log k}$, so

$$\frac{f(n)}{k^n} = 2^{(\log n)^2 - n \log k}.$$

Here, for any constant $k > 1$, the term $n \log k$ grows way faster than $(\log n)^2$, so the exponent goes to $-\infty$. This means

$$\frac{f(n)}{k^n} \rightarrow 0,$$

and $f(n)$ grows slower than any exponential.

Conclusion.

$$\boxed{f(n) = 2^{(\log n)^2}}$$

4 Exercise A.4

Consider a bipartite graph $G = (U \cup W, E)$. Prove that the sum of the degrees of the vertices of U is equal to the sum of the degrees of the vertices of W .

Proof.

By definition of a bipartite graph, each edge has exactly one endpoint in each set U and W .

Therefore, for every $e \in E$, the edge contributes one degree to U and one degree to W .

If there are $|E| = n$ edges, the total degree sum of the vertices in U is n , and likewise for W . Hence,

$$\sum_{u \in U} \deg(u) = \sum_{w \in W} \deg(w).$$

Q.E.D.

5 Exercise A.5

Let $k \geq 2$ and $n = 2k$. We consider all sets of k distinct integers from $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. We build a graph $G = (V, E)$, where each vertex represents one of these k -element subsets, and two vertices are adjacent if their corresponding sets have at least one element in common. Is G connected?

Proof. For each $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, let S_i be the set of all vertices corresponding to subsets that contain i . By combinatorics, there are

$$|S_i| = \binom{2k-1}{k-1}$$

such sets.

Now, consider two elements $i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ with $i \neq j$. The set of vertices corresponding to subsets containing both i and j is $S_i \cap S_j$. The number of such subsets is

$$|S_i \cap S_j| = \binom{2k-2}{k-2}.$$

Since $k \geq 2$, we have $\binom{2k-2}{k-2} > 0$. Hence, there exists at least one vertex (set) that contains both i and j .

Thus, for every pair (i, j) , the subgraph created by S_i and the subgraph created by S_j share at least one common vertex. Because each S_i is connected (all its vertices share element i), and all such subgraphs intersect pairwise, their union forms a single connected component.

Therefore, all vertices of G belong to one connected component.

$\therefore G$ is connected.

Q.E.D.

6 Exercise A.6

Problem. We saw that bipartite graphs do not contain K_3 . Find a graph H such that no bipartite graph contains H , and K_3 is not a subgraph of H .

Solution. Consider the graph C_5 :

Proof. We must show both $K_3 \not\subset C_5$ and that for any bipartite graph G , $C_5 \not\subset G$.

1. Show that $K_3 \not\subset C_5$.

Suppose that $K_3 \subset C_5$. Then C_5 would contain three mutually adjacent vertices. However, in C_5 , each vertex is adjacent only to two others, and there are no triangles (3-cycles). Hence, C_5 contains no subgraph isomorphic to K_3 . Therefore,

$$K_3 \not\subset C_5.$$

2. Show that C_5 is not a subgraph of any bipartite graph G .

Suppose $C_5 \subset G$ for some bipartite G . Then G must contain an odd cycle, since C_5 is an odd cycle. But a graph is bipartite if and only if it contains no odd cycles, which is a contradiction. Therefore,

$$C_5 \not\subset G \quad \text{for all bipartite graphs } G.$$

Conclusion. Since C_5 contains no K_3 and cannot appear as a subgraph of any bipartite graph, it satisfies the required conditions.

Q.E.D.

7 Exercise A.7

Problem. Consider $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in \mathbb{R}$ that satisfy

$$a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n = 1.$$

Prove that

$$a_1^2 + a_2^2 + \dots + a_n^2 \geq \frac{1}{n}.$$

Explain why a better lower bound is not possible.

Consider two sequences,

$$\{a_n\} = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\} \quad \text{and} \quad \{b_n\} = \{1, 1, \dots, 1\},$$

each of n elements.

Applying the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality, we get

$$\left(\sum_{j=1}^n |a_j b_j| \right)^2 \leq \left(\sum_{j=1}^n a_j^2 \right) \left(\sum_{j=1}^n b_j^2 \right).$$

Simplifying, we have

$$\left(\sum_{j=1}^n a_j \right)^2 \leq n \sum_{j=1}^n a_j^2.$$

Since $\sum a_j = 1$, this gives

$$1 \leq \sqrt{n \sum_{j=1}^n a_j^2} \implies \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \leq \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n a_j^2}.$$

Squaring (inequality preserved since both sides are positive), we get

$$\frac{1}{n} \leq a_1^2 + a_2^2 + \dots + a_n^2.$$

We can prove this is the lowest bound using Lagrange multipliers. We can say:

$$\nabla f = \lambda \nabla g,$$

where $f(a_1, \dots, a_n) = a_1^2 + \dots + a_n^2$ and $g(a_1, \dots, a_n) = a_1 + \dots + a_n - 1$.

Then

$$\langle 2a_1, 2a_2, \dots, 2a_n \rangle = \langle \lambda, \lambda, \dots, \lambda \rangle,$$

so $2a_i = \lambda$ for all i , which gives $a_i = \frac{\lambda}{2}$.

Plugging into the constraint:

$$n \cdot \frac{\lambda}{2} = 1 \implies \lambda = \frac{2}{n} \implies a_i = \frac{1}{n}.$$

Plugging this back in,

$$n \left(\frac{1}{n} \right)^2 = \frac{1}{n}.$$

Therefore, the smallest bound is $\frac{1}{n}$.

Q.E.D.